

SEGMENTATION OF ORGANS AND TUMOR WITHIN BRAIN MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGES USING K-NEAREST NEIGHBOR CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract: We investigate the topic of categorizing cancers of the brain using MRI scans. This challenge is frequently handled utilizing artificial intelligence approaches that acquire information from education mind pictures and then extrapolate to fresh evaluate minds. Yet, this technique confronts various hurdles that diminish its usefulness, including the capacity to accurately execute numerous mind position, connect the mental atlas, and identify relevant multidimensional characteristics that allow successful adaptation. These techniques are not straightforward and exhausting, restricting their use in medical centers. In this study, we suggest addressing these challenges by seeing what is happening as an issue of specialization dilemma inside the neural network. We present a partially automatic technique for segmenting a specific mind by developing and extrapolating just inside the brain in question while requiring minimum user input. We look at the method to integrate the number of closest neighbors (kNN), possibly the most basic machine learning approach known, into the cheapest characteristic vector (raw MRI data + position (x,y,z)) in a straightforward, precise, and rapid manner.

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization classifies brain tumors into benign and malignant tumors. Benign tumors are harmless, non-cancerous and slow-growing. On the other hand, they are also called low-grade tumors (grades I and II). Malignant tumors are aggressive, heterogeneous and spread rapidly to the brain and other parts of the body. These are known as high-grade tumors. These also affect high-grade tumors (grades III and IV), which are dangerous and life-threatening to the patient. Early diagnosis of brain tumors are important for treatment and improvement the prognosis [1]. There are several ways to diagnose brain tumors, including computed tomography (CT), electroencephalography (EEG), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Magnetic resonance imaging uses magnetic fields and radio waves to produce images of the internal organs of the human body. It is a high-resolution technology, and therefore provides valuable information images. According to the research community, MRI technology can be used to automatically determine the location and size of brain tumors without human intervention [2]. Although MRI provides an accurate and clear picture of the 2D and 3D shape of the brain, manual MRI classification is challenging and error-prone. It is difficult for radiologists to identify tumors and compare their tissue to nearby normal tissue. Thus human diagnosis is difficult, time consuming and errors could be happened leading to fault in diagnosis and treatment [3]. As a result using an automatic computerised system is important for accuracy and saving time. This system helps doctors and radiologists diagnose and classify brain tumors using innovative computer-aided diagnostic design (CAD). Computer-aided diagnosis is an important research topic in the fields of radiology and medical imaging, especially in the field of cancer staging. Computer-aided diagnosis

involves three steps: Remove noise from the image, segment the tumor region, and extract features from the segmented image[4].

2. Brain tumors classification

Automated segmentation and classification of brain tumors has attracted significant attention from researchers. **Developing a system that can accurately identify tumors without human intervention is difficult.** In illustration, Figure 1 shows a general classification scheme for brain tumors. As shown in Figure 1, the main steps are preprocessing, segmentation of medical MRI images, feature extraction, selection of the most relevant images, and finally application of machine learning algorithms [5]. Each step is explained in the following.

Figure 1. General block diagram of brain tumor classification

2.1 Data Acquisition

The components of the human body, such as water, bone, fat, and iron, affect medical imaging because they affect medical imaging techniques and principles[6]. X-ray produces high amount of radiation that affects the human body and may causes cancer or skin diseases. PET scans detect radiation produced by radioactive substances injected into human organs, thus showing the functioning of some parts of the human body and also obtaining clear images of those parts. However, MRI produces a strong magnetic field, which shows the details of organs from different angles. MRI machines work in two modes: the first uses a high magnetic field to obtain high-quality images, and the second uses a low magnetic field to make simple diagnoses. This tool allows for accurate visualization of abnormal brain tissues such as tumors, strokes, and hemorrhages.

2.2 Pre-processing

Preprocessing removes noise and artifacts such as time and date, and improves image quality to prepare it for segmentation. The next step depends on it, so researchers will determine if more time is needed to address it [7]. This procedure is carried out using several approaches such as cropping, picture resizing, equalizing the histogram, sorting, and image normalizing.

2.2.1 Resizing Image

image resizing changes pixel of image ,height and width to 512 x 512. Due to the very small size of image makes the detection of objects during the segmentation impossible , the image resizing is essential before the segmentation process[8] .

Since this study uses general feature extraction, the image resizing process also acts as a dependent variable, with the image size significantly affecting the obtained results.

2.2.2 Median Filtering

This process improves the image quality by elimination noise . the median of the specified mask environment detects the value of the output pixel by observe the middle value [8].

2.2.3 Cropping Image

In this step, brain objects are detected, which will be used in the next processing, the image is cropped, and background objects that are not necessary for the next processing are removed. Image cutting lowers elements that could alter the outcomes of the acquired characteristics, including mistakes in the detection of tumor items throughout the segmentation procedure. [8].

2.3 Segmentation

Segmentation is the most important step of image processing , in which the essential area for detection whether the area is affected. However Segmentation of brain tumor MRI images has many problems which includes the following : low contrast, loss boundaries, noise in the image ,varying in tissue types and changing in the intensities within tissues [9]. Segmentation is classified in several ways [10] :

- ✓ threshold-based: this approach presumes that classification of pixels to one class depending on its existing in a specific range[11].
- ✓ The zone-based technique assumes that neighboring pixels in an area share similar attributes [12].
- ✓ boundary-based approach: it supposes that pixels' characteristics change suddenly from region to another at the boundary line [13].
- ✓ pixel classification techniques: this technique classify the pixels based on feature space which is related the gray level, the colour components, and the local texture [14].

Combining two or more of these strategies generates a strategy termed a mixture [15].

This process determines the location of the tumor on the image. This process utilizes the results obtained in segmentation on the material obtained in feature extraction, which is useful for the next process. This study's disintegration phases include structural activities, the binarization procedure floodfill, expansion, subsidence, and drainage.

2.3.1 Morphological Transformation.

At Morphological Transformation the pre-processed image is edge detected in order to find the aim object which is been looked for as well as the object and background are both separated . T2 images are processed by edge detection. While in T1 image images are processed by color detection using the Morphological

Open. However the essential idea we should know that kernel value must be detected first by functions provided from open cv in order to detection objects [8].

2.3.2 Binarization

In this stage the pixel of the image is changed into a binary number by using the method of thresholding. First, specify the binary number that you require to discover. Then, set both the upper and lower limits of the binary value [8].

2.3.3 Flood Fill

Flood fill is an algorithm for determining the region associated with a particular node in a multidimensional matrix. The goal of this step is to combine the background color of the image with the background color of the brain object so that the brain object is detected as white in the remaining black background image. These microorganisms could be tumors or brain organs such as the brain stem[8].

2.3.4 Opening dan Closing

In this step, small noises that do not represent the objects of interest, especially the tumor, are removed. These small noises represent small brain organs that were discovered during previous surgeries. Reaming is performed prior to cutting the hole. The image from the previous stage is considered as input along with the kernel values. Unlike the open phase, in the closed phase, black dots and noise are removed from the selected objects, making them clearer. The inputs of this stage are the results of the performed open operation and the kernel values[8].

2.3.5 Dilation

To improve the clear representation of the item, the preceding image is somewhat distorted and expanded.

The next step receives the outcome of the preceding completion manage, the kernel's worth, and the next iteration.

2.3.6 Watershed

In order to understand this stage, we can consider high intensity as hills when grayscale images are seen from the surface of topography, while low intensity is considered as valleys. All valleys will be filled with water, if any valley is fully filled. Then there is a need to a barrier to prevents water from blending. watershed results different colors which don't confuse with each other between objects and It gets clear among the component and the backdrop.

OpenCV's watershed algorithm outperforms competing libraries in that it uses labels to identify which points in the watershed should be joined and which should not. The colors used are HSV colors.

2.4 Feature extraction techniques

In this step a new set of features which have the same information of the original features is created ,then the features' number is reduced . however the new ones are completely different. This process improves the accuracy, minimizes the risk of overfitting and speeds the training [16] .the image resulting from segmentation process is the input for feature extraction technique.

The acquired tumor has a white body and a black backdrop. The information that is entered follows up with processing utilizing the first column identification to locate the item under handled.

2.4.1 Filled Area

This process detects the area of the selected object. The calculation of this area is possible in spite of the irregular shape. This process is optimal for non-rounded tumors. First, the entries are named. Depending on the edge detection results, one record may consist of multiple labels. **The spatial results of the classified objects are not used as features in the classification process because they are first compared with the surrounding space or image space. The result is a comparison coefficient that represents the value used for one object [8].**

2.4.2 Centroid

The tumor location is determined by the centroid. First, the center of the object is determined, then x and y lines are drawn from this point to obtain the x and y coordinate values. **The input data for this function is the same as that of the Fill Local function. However, the obtained values are not used immediately in the allocation process. The combined results are then analyzed to identify the tumor's location. Initially the x and y planes are separated into different zones. The acquired coordinates for x and y are compared to the values of the area borders, which include regions 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 on x and y. Each zone (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5) has its own spectrum number. The position of the position number represents the total amount of areas contained in the geographic area and is employed as a categorization property.[8].**

2.5 Feature selection techniques

In this technique features in the dataset will be volume reduced, however these features are still the same. At this stage features are ordered from top to bottom regardless of their importance. Top features are mainly used for classification, in the other hand the bottom features are negligible[17]. Due to the time consuming and the possibility of faults, a supervised machine learning such as C5 algorithm is used in order to choose the best features.

3. Classification

Classification methods contain two methods mainly, these methods are detailed in the following:

3.1 Supervised methods

Supervised methods have two main stages:

The first one is training, in which extracted features are used in order to label the data carefully. In this stage after building the model, unlabeled classes are then specified. Supervised methods are preferred to unsupervised methods due to the possibility of fault in data labelling caused by human intervention.

In the next subsection, we will discuss some classifiers including K-NN (k Nearest Neighbor). K-NN is a basic method utilized in many sectors, including medical care, multimedia acknowledgment, financing, and handwritten. This algorithm works by calculating the nearest neighbor of an already unknown node that is classified as unknown. The distance between points is estimated utilizing techniques that include Hamming separation, Manhattan distance, the Euclid distance, the Minkowski separation, and so on, as determined by the kind of application.

To explain the algorithm, let's consider a scenario where we have two classes: class 1 (red) and class 2 (green), as shown in Figure 2. Suppose a new data point is added to the data set, highlighted in grey. The question is, into which category should this item fall? According to the KNN algorithm, several steps need to be performed to classify a point:

The total quantity of neighbors (K) is determined by the total amount of retrieved features/cases. By standard, K is set to 5 [18].

- Use the methods provided in Figure 2 B to identify the newly created point's closest neighbors.
- Calculate the total amount of observations in every group from these neighbors.
- As illustrated in figure 2C, allocate the newly acquired data point to the group containing many neighbors.

Support Vector Machines (SVM) can be used for both classification and regression problems, but are typically used for classification problems. The technique creates multiple n-dimensional spaces dependent on the amount of items used to form observations or examples. Every item corresponds to a location. The Support Vector Machine technique aims to discover an intersection or boundary in the space with n dimensions, called as a hyperspace, that divides each class. There are various possibilities to draw different super levels, but the best super level is the one with the maximum level. The maximum value is defined as the distance between the extreme data points between the classes, known as the support vector. This allows new data points to be classified with more confidence [19].

Figure 2. K-NN algorithm

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are a field of AI that arose in the 1940s, when scientists McCulloch and Pitts developed the first artificial neural network model. These networks imitate the way humans think and may acquire knowledge and accumulate knowledge as conventional cells. This capability makes them useful for a variety of applications in building automated systems. An artificial neural network consists of an input that passes a signal to a hidden layer, which performs a nonlinear transformation to produce a result in the output layer.

One form of artificially generated neural network classification is a feedforward neural network (FNN), that has been utilized in several investigations. The structure of this network is basic since information goes in a single guidance: from the information input level to the concealed layer, and then to the final layer [20]. Reverse propagation, biological algorithms, optimization of particle swarms, and synthetic honeybee colonies are examples of techniques used for training feedback networks of neurons. Yet, they have disadvantages like considerable computing expenses, the necessity to optimise many variables, and degradation of data from neighboring layers.

Recently, the application of deep learning has had an important effect on several domains, notably language recognition, computer vision, robotics, and CAD. Deep learning models have the ability to process raw data and achieve high performance, providing advantages over traditional machine learning methods. These benefits involve the capacity to interact immediately with unprocessed information like photos, fewer hours used, less skill necessary, and less exertion needed for setting up essential functions. Various architectures have been developed to represent deep learning models, with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) being the most common image processing model. CNNs are widely used in many applications due to their ability to well extract features and recognize patterns in images[21].

The CNN architecture comprises of three basic layers: visual neurons, data gathering, and fully connected layers. The initial layer serves as the primary feature extractor, identifying boundaries and edges within images. This layer can autonomously learn numerous filters simultaneously to achieve the desired predictive outcomes for the training dataset. Subsequent layers focus on data reduction, reducing the size of the objects created in the previous layers and reducing the computational resources required. The final layer, the fully connected layer, consists of neurons connected to every single cell from the preceding layer. This layer serves as a categorization method, allocating the attributes matrix created by previous ones to particular groups. [22].

3.2 Unsupervised methods

Unsupervised methods use an algorithm in order to classify image pixels to different classes automatically. Due to grouping pixels in unsupervised methods, training a model is no more demanded. Some of these methods include K-means clustering, which partitions pixels or data points into similar clusters. Clustering has two types: hard clustering and soft clustering. Strict clustering indicates whether a sample or pixel belongs to a group without overlapping between groups. Soft clustering means that a sample or pixel must belong to a group that allows overlap.

K-means is a simple unsupervised clustering method. However, this is time-consuming due to the huge number of iterations. Although choosing the right number of groups (K) will give an accurate separation, the outcomes might be inaccurate. In actual time grouping, the value of the variable K can be uncertain, requiring the method to be run repeatedly with various amounts of K. During every round, the gap among the information item and the closest cluster is computed and added. Additional computation and time are necessary.

Fuzzy C-means (FCM) is a type of clustering that enables units to collaborate on identical information. Dunn introduced this strategy in 1973, and Besdek built on it in 1981. It is frequently employed in recognizing patterns and is appropriate for separation of medical pictures [23]. The primary disadvantage of this approach is its sensitivity to interference and potential mistakes in distance calculation. The initial obstacle has been overcome in various research, such as [24], that offered anatomical data and processing approach for minimizing noise.

3.3 Hybrid techniques

When one or more techniques are used, this is known as Hybrid. Hybrid techniques are highly accurate due to decreasing the disadvantages of used methods and increasing their advantages. A study combined between FCM and SVM for segmentation brain diseases. FCM detected the affected areas in the brain, while SVM classified it [25].

4. Literature review

Several studies have conducted brain tumor classification by MRI images. For this target, Machine Learning (ML) has been used. ML starts with data cleaning, features extraction and detection of the most valuable features. Finally, the labeled samples are used for classification in case of supervised learning and prediction using unique samples. ML, or machine learning, is divided into two categories: controlled and uncontrolled approaches. The first kind builds a system for classification from a dataset with labels through giving it incoming information and modifying its model parameters appropriately. Additional information is then entered into the mathematical framework to evaluate or forecast the framework. This kind of method includes Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN) algorithms. [26].

Yoganathan's 2022 work developed an automated learning strategy for segmenting OAR and tumors from regular T1 and T2 brain MRI data. All library photos were placed in identical geographic location using a basic yet strict verification. The previous classification information was characterized using a KNN model, and the model that was learned was utilized to forecast the OAR and tumor radius. Twelve brain tumor patients were retrospectively registered and all images were normalized to the same spatial coordinates using a simple strict registration. Zones with significance were defined for dividing systems and malignancies. A k-nearest neighbor (KNN) categorization approach was employed to define previous integration information utilizing 15 picture parameters (T1 and T2 picture difficulty, four filtering Gabor pictures, six picture slopes, and three Horizontal dimensions). The model that was taught was subsequently

utilized for forecasting tissue outlines and tumors. Segmentation performance was evaluated using similarity coefficient cube (DSC), surface uniformity cube, sensitivity, specificity, and Hausdorff distance.

Yoganathan's study showed that semi-automated segmentation closely matched the ground truth. The average DSC values ranged from 0.49 (optic nerve cross section) to 0.89 (right eye) for organ segmentation and 0.87 for tumor segmentation [27].

Ramdlon [28] performed an investigation of categorising data from the Cancer Image Archive (TCIA). The data collected included magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans patients with astrocytoma, glioma, and oligodendroglioma-type brain tumours. A tumour grading system was developed to detect tumours and oedema in T1 and T2 scanning frames and categorise them accordingly. The data from using an arrangement was interpreted only on the basis of axial CT-MRI results, which were divided into three categories: a tumour, cancer of the brain, and oligodendroglioma. Basic image processing techniques, including enhancement of imagery, the image multiplying, topological pictures, and hydrological pictures, were employed to detect tumour regions.

Otherwise in 2014, Havaei suggested a manually operated approach for segmenting an individual mind by developing and expanding just inside the brain in question while requiring minimum user intervention. He investigated the idea of integrating the k closest neighbors (kNN), possibly the most basic artificial intelligence algorithm known, using the smallest vector of characteristics (raw MRI data + position (x, y, z)) in a straightforward, reliable, and rapid manner. The publicly available BRATS database revealed that the approach is quick and offers the second highest efficiency when speaking of total division of tumors and foundation test collection. [29].

5. Conclusions

K-Nearest Neighbor method results high accurate consequences when it is used to classify the brain tumors. In order to get auto detection, excellent and accurate consequences from segmentation process, Machine learning method is demanded[8]. Yet, the precision of the method for categorizing may be impaired not only by the model and test or validation functions used, but also by the distribution of the training data. Factors that can affect the segmentation outcome can be taken into account during the preprocessing step to improve the accuracy of the segmentation process.

K-NN based semi-automatic segmentation process MRI images in fast and accurate way, it is also a planning method for MRI-guided radiotherapy[27].

In future work, it's preferred to more development of the idea which based on machine learning classifiers in brain generalization, such as kernel SVMs, other than kNN as well as improving the accuracy.

Also, a fully automatic variant should be investigated in order to avoid the manual interaction, thus the initially detected tumours regions would be automatically selected [29].

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